

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 142

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 142

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 142:0 †Maskil of David, when he was in the cave. A Prayer.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 142:1 מִשְׁכִּיל לְדָוִד בְּהִיזְתּוֹ בְּמַעְרָה תְּפִלָּה : 2 קוֹלִי אֶל־יְהוָה אֲזַעֵק קוֹלִי אֶל־יְהוָה אֶתְחַנֵּן : 3 אֲשַׁפֵּד לְפָנָיו שִׁיחֵי צָרָתִי לְפָנָיו אֶגִּיד : 4 בְּהִתְעַטֵּף עָלַי אֲרוּחֵי וְאַפָּה יִדְעֵת נְתִיבָתִי בְּאַרְחֵי אֶתְלַךְ שָׁמְנוּ פֶתַח לִי : 5 תִּבְיֹט יָמִיךְ וּדְרָאֵה וְאֵין־לִי מִכִּיר אֲבָד מְנוּס מִמֶּנִּי אֵין דּוֹרֵשׁ לְנַפְשִׁי : 6 זַעֲקָתִי אֶל־יְהוָה אֲמַרְתִּי אַתָּה מִחְסֵי תִלְקֵי בְּאַרְצֵךְ תִּחְיִים : 7 תִּקְשִׁיבָה אֶל־רִנָּתִי כִּי־דִלֹתִי מְאֹד הִצִּילָנִי מִדָּבָר כִּי אֲמַצּוּ מִמֶּנִּי : 8 הֲוֹצִיָאֵה מִמִּסְגָּר אֲנַפְשִׁי לְהוֹדוֹת אֶת־שִׁמְךָ בִּי יִכְתְּרוּ צַדִּיקִים כִּי תִגְמַל עָלַי :</p>
<p>Psa. 142:1 I ^acry aloud with my voice to the LORD;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">I ^bmake supplication with my voice to the LORD.</p> <p>² I ^apour out my complaint before Him;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">I declare my ^btrouble before Him.</p> <p>³ When ^amy spirit ¹was overwhelmed within me,</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">You knew my path.</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">In the way where I walk</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">They have ^bhidden a trap for me.</p> <p>⁴ Look to the right and see;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">For there is ^ano one who regards me;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">¹There is no ^bescape for me;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">¹No one cares for my soul.</p>	
<p>Psa. 142:5 I cried out to You, O LORD;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">I said, “You are ^amy refuge,</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">My ^bportion in the ‘land of the living.</p> <p>⁶ ““Give heed to my cry,</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">For I am ^bbrought very low;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">Deliver me from my persecutors,</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">For they are too ‘strong for me.</p> <p>⁷ ““Bring my soul out of prison,</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">So that I may give thanks to Your name;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">The righteous will surround me,</p>	

For You will ^b deal bountifully with me.”	
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References

Psalm 142:0

[†]Possibly *Contemplative*, or *Didactic*, or *Skillful Psalm*

[°]1 Sam 22:1; 24:3

Psalm 142:1

^aPs 77:1

^bPs 30:8

Psalm 142:2

^aPs 102: title

^bPs 77:2

Psalm 142:3

¹Lit *fainted*

^aPs 77:3; 143:4

^bPs 140:5

Psalm 142:4

¹Lit *Escape has perished from me*

^aPs 31:11; 88:8, 18

^bJob 11:20; Jer 25:35

^cJer 30:17

Psalm 142:5

^aPs 91:2, 9

^bPs 16:5; 73:26

^cPs 27:13

Psalm 142:6

^aPs 17:1

^bPs 79:8; 116:6

^cPs 18:17

Psalm 142:7

^aPs 143:11; 146:7

^bPs 13:6

Targum

Psa. 142:1 A good lesson, composed by David when he was in the cave; a prayer. ² With my voice I will cry out in the presence of the LORD; with my voice I will pray in the presence of the LORD. ³ I will pour out my speech in his presence; I will tell of my trouble in his presence. ⁴ When my spirit grows weary against me, you know my path; on this road that I will walk, they have hidden a trap for me. ⁵ I looked to the right and saw, and there was no-one acknowledging me; deliverance has vanished from me, and there is none who avenges my soul. ⁶ I cried out to you, O LORD; I said, “You are my deliverer, my portion in the land of the living.” ⁷ Hear my prayer, for I have become very poor; deliver me from my persecutors, for they are too strong for me. ⁸ Deliver my soul from prison, to confess your name; for my sake the righteous will make for you a glorious crown, for you will repay me with goodness.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

David had a difficult time as he fled from Saul. The events of David's life emulated what Israel would go through centuries later. David was one person standing before a small army. Judah became a small nation with enemies that surrounded her. She needs to learn the lesson of how David survived. David called upon the LORD constantly to help him.

Notes on this Psalm

There are several Psalms which teach us to call upon the LORD for help during good and bad times. In this Psalm, David calls out to the LORD for help. When everything looks gloomy, call out to the LORD. Perhaps a better thing to do is to always pray to the LORD for help. Then if sometime terrible happens, the LORD will know your name and will come to your rescue.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

